

Review

The Role of Family in Child's Mental Health

Jean Pierre Mugiraneza^{a*}, Lambert Kwizera^b, Ambroise Nzabasanga^c, Dr. Ildephonse Habinshuti^{d,e}, Felix Banderembaho^f

^aMount Kenya University, P.O. Box 5826 Kigali, Rwanda

^bUniversity of Rwanda, P.O. Box 4285, Kigali

^cUniversity of Lay Adventists of Kigali (UNILAK), P.O. Box 6392 Kigali, Rwanda

^dOrganization of African Academic Doctors (OAAD), Off Kamiti Road P.O. Box 25305-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

^eUniversity of Rwanda, College of Agriculture, Animal Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, School of Agriculture and Food Sciences, Department of Food Science, P.O. Box 210 Musanze, Rwanda

^fUniversity of Rwanda/College of Medicine and Health Sciences/School of Medicine and Pharmacy, P.O. Box 3286 Kigali, Rwanda

Abstract: **Background:** Child's mental health around the world is important to consider. More than 13% of young people age 10-19 have a mental disorder. Despite several initiatives that have been put in place to deal with child mental health, the importance of the family in mental health of the child is still critical. Parenting styles affect psychology of children in one way or another. There exist four parenting styles which are; authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and uninvolved. **Objective:** This review aims to explore the role of family, through the lens of parenting styles in child's mental health. **Participants and Setting:** The Participants are children and Adolescents aged less than 18 years. **Methods:** This Review was conducted from May, 2023 to January, 2024. Studies used were published by researchers between 2019-2023. The study followed Jesson & Lacey's critical literature review methodology, utilizing academic databases like PubMed and Google Scholar, as well as WHO and official public health websites. **Results:** The review indicated the parenting approaches have positive and negative impacts on child mental health. These approaches include authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and uninvolved. There are psychological factors that influence the birth of these styles among parents. **Conclusions:** Parenting style plays a greater role on overall mental health of the children. Parents should promote their children's self-esteem by showing them a lot of emotional support, avoiding rejection, and refraining from being overly protective. To enhance their children's self-esteem and psychological adaptability.

Keywords: Parent's Mental Health, Parenting style, a family, Child's Mental Health.

*Corresponding Author : Jean Pierre Mugiraneza, Tel :+250785213758, E-mail: mugijpierre@gmail.com

Accepted: 15 June, 2024; **Published:** 17 June, 2024

How to cite this article: Jean Pierre Mugiraneza (2024). The Role of Family in Child's Mental Health. *North American Academic Research*, 7(6), 28-41. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12769880>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Child and adolescent mental health has received a great deal of attention around the world and become a public health issue.¹ It is estimated that on a worldwide scale, approximately 13% of individuals aged 10-19 face a mental

disorder, equating to one out of every seven in this age group, contributing significantly to the overall burden of disease.² Mental health of children in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC), as found in literature, has been particularly associated with war, conflict and displacement, natural disasters, poverty⁴, child labor and other forms of exploitation. Moreover, from policy perspective to tackle this issue of child mental illness, this problem has been exacerbated by stigma, limited policy input, lack of contextualized evidence and limited research efforts in LMIC.³ Moreover, it is estimated that one in eight children aged 4-18 years, in high income countries, suffering from mental illness or disorders, does not receive the treatment. Mental disorders include anxiety, attention-deficit/hyperactivity, oppositional defiant, substance use, conduct, and depression.⁵ Anxiety and depressive disorders among boys and girls are more prevalent around the world (See Figure 1). These disorders make up around 43 percent.⁶

2. Research questions:

- a) What is the scope, nature and extent of a Family on child's mental health and behavior of individuals?
- b) How the Parenting styles affect psychologically on child's and adolescents' mental health?
- c) What are the Solutions and strategies for a child protection get achieved?

3. Methods

Utilizing academic databases like PubMed and Google Scholar, as well as WHO and official public health websites. This critical literature review aimed to explore the role of family, through the lens of parenting styles in child's mental health and of adolescents as well and proposing the solutions for a child protection get achieved globally as a child is concern of the globe.

3.1. Eligibility criteria

The criteria for inclusion were: (1) participants were children and adolescents aged under 18years with a background of being raised in certain family with certain parenting style. (2) Studies were required to meet the criteria outlined in Table 1. (3) Studies used published from 2019 up to 2023.

3.2. Searches

This Review was conducted from May, 2023 to January, 2024. Studies used were published by researchers between 2019-2023, 107 articles were used but 54 studies were cited. The study followed Jesson & Lacey's critical literature review methodology.

4. Results

4.1 Prevalence of important mental disorders among adolescents globally, 2019

Various efforts to deal with child mental health have been put in place, such as psychosocial interventions,³ and adoption of western mental health system.⁷ Studies have indicated there is a role of families in dealing the child mental health, alongside with their engagement in seeking mental health services for their child with mental health issues.⁸ It has been argued that child mental health is a family issue, affair or a problem, probably due to the fact there is a relationship between parental mental health problems and child mental health outcomes. It has been observed that the dysfunctional relationship between the parent and child is a significant vehicle for mental disorders in children.⁹ Studies indicate the poor mental health of the parents or caregivers influence the child mental health. It leads to poor mental health of the children. There is a significant association with poor child mental health.¹⁰ In addition to this, mental health problems among the children have been associated with the family structure, however, there is a debate that parental education, socio-economic status, employment status, family history of mental health problems are not the factors leading to child mental health.¹¹

Figure 1.

4.2. Importance of the families in Child’s Mental Health

Families play a critical role in the development of child mental health. This role involves provision of parental care, provision of good nutrition, provision of support such as giving attention, motivating to learn, promotion of positive attitudes, creating harmonious atmosphere in families, promoting integrity, and imparting religious values among the children. All these roles affect the growth of child mental health.⁸ Studies have indicated that support and care from families are very important in children with mental disorders. This is emphasized by World Health Organization (WHO)’s statement that “families are essential partners in mental health care.”¹² Families are essential to children’s treatment and rehabilitation from addiction or mental health issues. Children’s mental health development needs a supportive and healthy home environment¹³. Moreover, parenting style is another component that needs to be considered in assessing its role in child mental health development. Parenting style consists of many factors that combine to create a mindset in which parents communicate their behavior and practices in raising their children. Parenting style not only shows the disciplined and responsible behavior of parents but also creates expectations for children. This involves communication through the parent’s body language, tone of voice, emotions and attention, in addition to what the parent says to the child and their overall behavior towards the child.¹⁴

There are four types of parenting style: Authoritarian, authoritative, permissive and nonconformist. The following table (Table 1) indicates their description as adapted from Thomson & Jacque (2017)¹⁵

4.3. Parenting Style

Table 1: Parenting Style

Parenting style	Definition
Authoritarian	The parent prioritizes submission and asserting their authority with force (being very demanding and not very responsive).
Authoritative	The parent fosters independence by being sensitive to the needs of children and making the most of available resources. The parent models effective engagement with others, provides interpersonal interactions with children, balancing reason and punishment, instills social and cultural values while fostering independence, and being highly responsive and demanding

Permissive	The parent encourages non-intrusive conduct while providing resources and support (being very responsive without being overly demanding).
Nonconformist	The parent rejects authority, is more controlling in their parenting than permissive parents are, and is less passive.

Parenting style affects the mental health of the child in a significant way.^{16,17} It has been observed that the behavior of parents can be a predicting factor of the child mental health.¹⁸ For example, parents, in their style, that demand physical discipline and with over-controlling behavior were found to have children that are likely to have mental health symptoms.¹⁹ This is a kind of hostile parenting which has a long lasting impact on mental health of the child and adolescent.²⁰

The well-being and self-esteem of children are strongly influenced by their parents or guardians who play a crucial role in shaping their character, helping them navigate life's challenges, and addressing their physical and emotional needs. Parenting style encompasses the behaviors and manners parents employ to create the emotional environment in which their child develops. A child's mental health is significantly impacted by their interactions with their parents, and the foundation for good mental health is laid early in life. Parents have a profound impact on promoting their children's overall well-being. Just as parental development and parenting can address behavioral issues, they also lay the groundwork for self-esteem in early childhood.²¹ Therefore this review attempts to assess how different parenting styles affect children's mental health.

4.4. Effects of Parenting Style on Child's mental health

Literature indicates that the parenting style does not only play a critical role in child development but also, significantly, on child mental health.^{14,17,18,20,22,23} Effective or positive parenting supports children in coping with non-social challenges and is essential for their early growth, emotional stability, and emotional maturation. Poor or negative parenting and instances of abuse can result in depression and health issues among the children.²⁴ Parenting style has positive and negative effects on child mental health, and has an influence on child behaviour.²⁵

5. Discussion

5.1. Positive and Negative Effects of Parenting Style

5.1.1. Authoritarian Parenting Style and Child's Mental Health

An authoritarian parent-child relationship is marked by imposing strict demands and offering limited responsiveness. It often involves one-way communication and clearly defined roles for both the parent and child. Children raised in such an environment are often subjected to inflexible rules that they are expected to adhere to without question. There is usually little room for them to express their opinions or negotiate with their parents. The child is expected to uphold these stringent standards without exception, and when mistakes occur, authoritarian parents may resort to punishments to enforce the rules.²⁶ Well-behaved children often have authoritarian parents, as they are accustomed to a structured discipline and the consequences of misbehavior. These children also tend to excel in organized environments with authoritative figures. However, those raised in an authoritarian atmosphere may develop a tendency towards rebellious behavior as they grow older. Additionally, they may encounter challenges in managing their anger in the future.²⁶

From positive side, an authoritarian parenting style has been associated with good mental health among the children under 19 years of age. For instance, this style has been associated with better mental health in Arab population.^{27,28} It has been well established that children raised in authoritarian families have good behavior, whereby children are aware of what is acceptable or not acceptable. These children exhibit the safety behavior, since they are aware of the harmful outcomes, and consider hard working to achieve or accomplish the goal.

But this style has negative effects on the children. Authoritarian parenting style among children under 19 have been associated with higher levels of distress, low self esteem and lack of coping strategies. This style causes psychological pressure among the children which results in having internal symptoms.²⁹ The study done in German among students

aged 14-17 years that have authoritarian parents revealed that these children have high levels of score of depersonalization, lower preferences of coping strategies, and higher levels of anxiety.²⁹ It has been observed that male children suffer from mental disorders in families with authoritarian parents.²² Other studies found that children that have grown in families that have authoritarian attitudes tend to have negative mental state, which is not fully developed, have the insecurity, feel unappreciated and lack confidence.³⁰ Furthermore, with this authoritarian parenting style, children may develop aggressive and negative behaviors.²³ One of the negative behaviors among children may be juvenile delinquency.²⁵ Children raised in families with authoritarian attitudes have tendency to develop high levels of emotional and behavioral problems²⁹. Authoritarian parenting has been associated with occurrence of depressive symptoms among the children.³¹

5.1.2. Authoritative Parenting Style and Child Mental Health

This parenting style involves providing their kids with strict boundaries while yet being responsive, caring, and supporting. By outlining expectations, having conversations, and using logic, they try to discipline kids. Children's opinions are heard, but they are not always accepted. Children reared in this manner typically grow up to be gregarious, vivacious, happy, independent, self-controlled, inquisitive, cooperative, and goal-oriented.³²

Authoritative parenting is considered as a suitable style for optimal child development,²³ and emotional stability, adaptive coping strategies and life satisfaction among the children.³¹ This parenting style has a critical role on psychological behavior and growth of the children. Children raised in this style exhibit low levels of aggressiveness.²³ In contrast with authoritarian parenting style, authoritative style has been associated with positive mental health.³³ Children from authoritative families are at a higher risk of experiencing depression, low self-worth, and various other psychological and mental health conditions.³⁴ Moreover, studies found that adolescents from authoritative families are less susceptible to mental health problems, and that male are more resilient than female and have stable mental and emotional states.³⁵ It has been observed that authoritative parenting has been associated with better mental health, and with low levels of stress among boys and higher levels of stress among girls. It has been even observed that this style is associated with low probability of occurrence of depression.¹⁷ It has been hypothesized that children who experience mostly authoritarian parenting are shielded from internalizing symptoms like anxiety and depression. This parenting style is a protective factor for child mental health problems and has beneficial effect.^{36,37} These effects are emotional well-being, which reduces the risk of depression, anxiety and other mental health problems among the children. They include also a sense of self-esteem and confidence, social skills, ability to deal with stressful moments in a constructive manner, and developed work ethic, self discipline and intrinsic motivation.³⁸ Moreover, children raised by authoritative parents are less likely to get involved in anti-social behaviors such as delinquency and drug use.³⁹

5.1.3. Permissive Parenting Style and Child's Mental Health

Parents that choose this parenting style are affectionate but indifferent. They neglect to enforce strict boundaries, keep a tight eye on their kids' activities, or demand that their kids behave in a way that is proper for their age. Children brought up in this manner typically exhibit traits of impulsivity, disobedience, aimlessness, aggression, dominance, and low levels of achievement, self-control, and self-reliance.³²

The traits of permissive parenting are low demands and strong attentiveness. Permissive parents are characterized as being comparatively warm, no demanding, and uncontrollably affectionate. The mental health of children has frequently been reported to suffer as a result of permissive parenting. Permissive parenting, for example, has been linked to worse psychological wellness. Additionally it has been linked to a child's risk of readmission to inpatient mental health facilities. These correlations suggest that this parenting style may also be linked to the parents' decision to seek and when they choose to seek care for their child's mental health issues.⁴⁰

Even while studies have shown that permissive parenting has a number of drawbacks, it's vital to recognize that this strategy also has certain positives. A loving and caring environment is fostered for their children by permissive par-

ents, who are frequently described as warm and receptive. Remarkably, some research has indicated that permissive parenting may have beneficial benefits on substance use prevention that are comparable to those of authoritative parenting. Additionally, studies show that children who grow up with permissive parents typically have strong self-esteem. Therefore, despite its shortcomings, permissive parenting offers advantages, especially when it comes to the development of children’s self-esteem, parental warmth, and protective effects.⁴¹⁻⁴³

Children raised by permissive parents typically lack a strong sense of self-discipline as they grow up since this parenting style comprises a lack of expectations and demands. Because there aren’t many boundaries in their family, they could be more mischievous at school and less eager to study than many of their friends (poor academic performance.^{41,44} Additionally, studies indicate that permissive parenting practices can have detrimental effects on children and increase social isolation, anxiety, and depression.⁴⁵

5.1.4. Nonconformist or uninvolved Parenting Style and Child’s Mental Health

Parents using this parenting style are unapproachable, unresponsive, and rejecting. Raised in this manner, children often have low self-esteem and lack confidence and look to other, sometimes inappropriate, role models to replace their neglectful parent.³² Parenting without affection, support, or direction for the children is known as uninvolved parenting. Parents who are cold, uninvolved, and “hands-off” when it comes to enforcing rules, regulations or boundaries in the family lack warmth. Negative behaviors, poor academic achievement, low self-esteem, and substance abuse are common outcomes of neglectful or uninvolved parenting.⁴⁶ This style has been associated with increased risk of depression and mental health problems, feelings of worthlessness, insecurity, and attachment disorders in children.^{47,48}

Furthermore, studies have indicated that uninvolved parenting is associated with lower self-esteem and lack of confidence among the children. These children tend to have behavioral issues like being impulsive and aggressive.⁴⁹ Teenagers raised by uninvolved parents lack social skills, have social anxiety, low self-esteem, have mental health problems, academic struggle, and have attachment problems⁵⁰. Due to uninvolved parents, children may become stressful due to lack of family support, emotionally withdrawn, fearing to be dependent on others, exposed to substance use, have to learn to provide for themselves and tend to be delinquent during their adolescence.⁵¹

5.2. Parenting Style detects Child’s mental health.

Figure 2:

5.3 Risks factors of Parenting Style

Parenting styles can vary based on cultural, ethnic, and economic aspects, as there are numerous factors that might influence parenting methods, such as social, political, and economic ones. Parenting styles are based on two primary criteria: parental control, which includes actions that influence the child’s behavior, and affection and acceptance, which includes encouraging and supporting pleasant emotions between parents and child.⁵²

There are psychological factors that affect the parenting style. They include the factors that affect parents include mental health, self-efficacy, stress from parenting, perfectionism, personality traits, childhood trauma, marital satisfaction, parents’ attachment style, perceived parenting style, and substance abuse; the factors that affect children include temperament, anxiety, and developmental and mental disabilities.⁵³

5.4. Influences on parenting can stem from internal factors such as the parent or child’s characteristics or external, socio-cultural characteristics.

Figure 3:

5.5. Parent’s Mental Health and Parenting style

Parenting styles are frequently closely linked to the mental health of parents. It’s clear that parents who are experiencing psychological anguish might be hostile and rejecting toward their own kids. These parents are likely to employ physical punishment and establish strict guidelines for behavior management. According to this, it has been demonstrated that an authoritarian parenting style is favorably connected with a history of serious depressive illnesses and

negatively correlated with authoritative parenting approaches. Additionally, parents who are depressed may not express positive attitudes toward their kids or may feel negatively about their parental responsibilities. On the other side, moms with bipolar disorder are more prone to interact with family members with greater hostility and to adopt an avoidant and insecure attachment style towards their children. A healthy coping mechanism, parents' compliance issues, and ultimately poor parenting can all be negatively impacted by anxiety as a stressor. Some parents may choose to parent by intimidating their kids, or they may parent and connect with their kids in a way that is marked by rejection and excessive control.⁵³

5.5.1 Parent stress

Parenting stress is one of the variables linked to a parent's traits. When parents are asked to do more as parents than they actually have the means to do, parental stress results. As a result, parents who experience more parenting stress tend to be less protective and more rejectionist. More stress in the home often translates into more discipline and less affection for the kids. Parenting-related stresses also include the stress of raising children and feeling restricted by their presence. It has also been noted that parents who experience stress related to parenting tend to become authoritarian parents. In a similar vein, stress related to parenting can make parents feel anxious and distressed, which can lead to irritability and aggressive tendencies.⁵³

5.5.2. Personality Traits

Parents with agreeable personality traits, characterized by their ability to obtain social support and avoid conflicts, are less likely to develop depression. They tend to adopt flexible and child-centered parenting approaches. Openness to new experiences, which involves emotional stability and a willingness to try new things, is associated with positive parenting, as having a child is a new experience. Conscientious parents, known for their discipline and good parenting roles, are also seen as appropriate models by their children.⁵³

5.5.3. Childhood trauma experience

A history of childhood abuse (physical, sexual, or emotional) among parents is considered a risk factor for negative parenting styles. Such maltreatment experienced by parents during their childhood can lead to interpersonal problems, including difficulties in interactions with their own children. It can also result in emotional issues like distrust, uncertainty, and avoidance of intimate relationships. Additionally, there's a connection between childhood abuse and adverse outcomes for parents, such as reduced parenting competence, increased parenting stress, less effective parenting styles, parental hostility, the use of physical punishment, and neglect of their own children. In essence, a history of maltreatment can create a lasting impact on children's development that persists into adulthood. Furthermore, mothers with a history of childhood sexual abuse may experience greater parenting stress, which can lead to reduced empathy for their own children.⁵³

5.5.4 Other factors

Other factors that affect parenting style include marital satisfaction, parents' attachment style, Self-efficacy, perfectionism, and perceived parenting style. In addition to this, there are other factors related to children that affect parenting style. These include: developmental and mental disabilities of children, child temperament, and anxiety among children.⁵³

5.5.5. Solutions to the Problem of Child Mental Health

It is factual that certain parenting styles are related to psychological disorders among the children. Several evidences indicate that these style play greater role on overall mental health of the children.⁵⁴ Parents should promote their children's self-esteem by showing them a lot of emotional support, avoiding rejection, and refraining from being overly protective. To enhance their children's self-esteem and psychological adaptability, parents should focus on providing ample emotional warmth, minimizing rejection and over-protectiveness. This will ultimately contribute to better mental well-being for their children. More precisely, parents should express love, care, affection, and emotional sup-

port to their children through physical, verbal, or symbolic gestures. They should refrain from showing indifference, aggression, neglect, or rejection towards their children, and avoid exerting excessive control over them.¹⁶

Parents should acquire knowledge of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) techniques, including acceptance, cognitive diffusion, and adaptable focus on the present, mindfulness, self-awareness, values, and determined action. This will help boost their psychological adaptability, improve the family environment, and strengthen the parent-child relationship. Simultaneously, these techniques can also be taught to children to reduce their psychological rigidity and foster better mental health.¹⁶

5.5.6. Limitations

This review has several limitations; firstly is a Multicultural limitation. Secondary is mental health Contextualization according to cultural differences. The third one is that the studies conducted on Family and Child's mental Health are not enough comparing the level of significance of Child Protection as a globe concern. Our review indicated the issues regarding to a significant and fundamental health to all a human being health. Is in that regard the nations should work on it hands to hands with all sectors and in all angles of life.

6. Conclusion

This review examines the impact of parenting styles on child mental health, highlighting the influence of authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, and uninvolved parenting styles. It suggests that psychological factors influence the emergence of these styles. The review recommends further research to understand the causal relationship between parenting styles and child mental health, and suggests future studies should consider specific regions or regions as defined by the World Bank.

References

1. Yu T, Xu J, Jiang Y, Hua H, Zhou Y, Guo X. School educational models and child mental health among K-12 students: a scoping review. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health*. 2022;16(1):32. doi:[10.1186/s13034-022-00469-8](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13034-022-00469-8)
2. UNICEF, ed. *On My Mind: Promoting, Protecting and Caring for Children's Mental Health*. UNICEF; 2021.
3. Vostanis P. Editorial: Global child mental health - emerging challenges and opportunities. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*. 2017;22(4):177-178. doi:[10.1111/camh.12246](https://doi.org/10.1111/camh.12246)
4. Abraham A, Walker-Harding L. The key social determinants of mental health: their effects among children globally and strategies to address them: a narrative review. *Pediatric Medicine*. 2022;5(0). doi:[10.21037/pm-20-78](https://doi.org/10.21037/pm-20-78)
5. Barican JL, Yung D, Schwartz C, Zheng Y, Georgiades K, Waddell C. Prevalence of childhood mental disorders in high-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis to inform policymaking. *Evidence-Based Mental Health*. 2022;25(1):36-44. doi:[10.1136/ebmental-2021-300277](https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmental-2021-300277)
6. UNICEF, ed. *The State of the World's Children 2021: On My Mind Promoting, Protecting and Caring for Children's Mental Health*. UNICEF; 2021.
7. Kopinak JK. Mental health in developing countries: Challenges and opportunities in introducing western mental health system in uganda. *International journal of MCH and AIDS*. 2015;3(1):22-30. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4948168/>
8. McKay MM, Bannon Jr WM. Engaging families in child mental health services. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America*. 2004;13(4):905-921. doi:[10.1016/j.chc.2004.04.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chc.2004.04.001)
9. Stracke M, Heinzl M, Müller AD, et al. Mental Health Is a Family Affair Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on the Associations between Mental Health Problems in Parents and Children during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2023;20(5):4485. doi:[10.3390/ijerph20054485](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20054485)

10. Wolicki SB, Bitsko RH, Cree RA, et al. Mental Health of Parents and Primary Caregivers by Sex and Associated Child Health Indicators. *Adversity and Resilience Science*. 2021;2(2):125-139. doi:[10.1007/s42844-021-00037-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s42844-021-00037-7)
11. Koning NR, Büchner FL, Verbiest MEA, Vermeiren RRJM, Numans ME, Crone MR. Factors associated with the identification of child mental health problems in primary care: a systematic review. *The European Journal of General Practice*. 2019;25(3):116-127. doi:[10.1080/13814788.2019.1623199](https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2019.1623199)
12. Fakhrou AA, Adawi TR, Ghareeb SA, Elsherbiny AM, AlFalasi MM. Role of family in supporting children with mental disorders in Qatar. *Heliyon*. 2023;9(8):e18914. doi:[10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18914](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18914)
13. Mphaphuli LK. The Impact of Dysfunctional Families on the Mental Health of Children. In: IntechOpen; 2023. doi:[10.5772/intechopen.110565](https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.110565)
14. Dalimonte-Merckling D, Williams JM. Parenting styles and their effects☆. In: Benson JB, ed. Elsevier; 2020:470-480. doi:[10.1016/B978-0-12-809324-5.23611-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809324-5.23611-0)
15. Thomson P, Jaque SV. 11 - attachment, parenting, and childhood adversity. In: Thomson P, Jaque SV, eds. Explorations in creativity research. Academic Press; 2017:167-186. doi:[10.1016/B978-0-12-804051-5.00011-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-804051-5.00011-1)
16. Peng B, Hu N, Yu H, Xiao H, Luo J. Parenting style and adolescent mental health: The chain mediating effects of self-esteem and psychological inflexibility. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2021;12. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.738170>
17. Vijay C, Gonsalves KP, Ramesh N. Parenting styles and mental health of adolescents: A cross-sectional study in south india. *Journal of Mental Health and Human Behaviour*. 2022;27(1):19. doi:[10.4103/jmhbb.jmhbb.176.20](https://doi.org/10.4103/jmhbb.jmhbb.176.20)
18. Azman Ö, Mauz E, Reitzle M, Geene R, Hölling H, Rattay P. Associations between parenting style and mental health in children and adolescents aged 11-17 years: Results of the KiGGS cohort study (second follow-up). *Children*. 2021;8(8):672. doi:[10.3390/children8080672](https://doi.org/10.3390/children8080672)
19. Katsantonis I, Symonds JE. Population heterogeneity in developmental trajectories of internalising and externalising mental health symptoms in childhood: differential effects of parenting styles. *Epidemiology and Psychiatric Sciences*. 2023;32:e16. doi:[10.1017/S2045796023000094](https://doi.org/10.1017/S2045796023000094)
20. Kumar K. Parenting style can significantly influence a child's mental health, new study finds. *ABC News*. Published online 2023. <https://abcnews.go.com/GMA/Family/parenting-style-significantly-influence-childs-mental-health-new/story?id=98266998>
21. Singh S. Parenting style in relation to children's mental health and self-esteem: A review of literature. *Indian Journal of Health and Well-being*. 2017;8:1522-1527.
22. Eun JD, Paksarian D, He JP, Merikangas KR. Parenting style and mental disorders in a nationally representative sample of US adolescents. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*. 2018;53(1):11-20. doi:[10.1007/s00127-017-1435-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-017-1435-4)
23. Masud H, Ahmad MS, Cho KW, Fakhr Z. Parenting Styles and Aggression Among Young Adolescents: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Community Mental Health Journal*. 2019;55(6):1015-1030. doi:[10.1007/s10597-019-00400-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-019-00400-0)
24. Lanjekar PD, Joshi SH, Lanjekar PD, Wagh V. The effect of parenting and the parent-child relationship on a child's cognitive development: A literature review. *Cureus*. 14(10):e30574. doi:[10.7759/cureus.30574](https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.30574)
25. Sarwar S. Influence of Parenting Style on Children's Behaviour. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*. 2016;3(2):222. doi:[10.22555/joeed.v3i2.1036](https://doi.org/10.22555/joeed.v3i2.1036)
26. Maddox LA. Types of parenting styles and their pros and cons. *BetterHelp*. Published online September 2023. <https://www.betterhelp.com/advice/parenting/types-of-parenting-styles-and-their-pros-and-cons/>

27. Palacios I, Garcia OF, Alcaide M, Garcia F. Positive parenting style and positive health beyond the authoritative: Self, universalism values, and protection against emotional vulnerability from spanish adolescents and adult children. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2022;13. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1066282>
28. Pinquart M, Kauser R. Do the associations of parenting styles with behavior problems and academic achievement vary by culture? Results from a meta-analysis. *Cultural Diversity & Ethnic Minority Psychology*. 2018;24(1):75-100. doi:[10.1037/cdp0000149](https://doi.org/10.1037/cdp0000149)
29. Azman Ö, Mauz E, Reitzle M, Geene R, Hölling H, Rattay P. Associations between parenting style and mental health in children and adolescents aged 1117 years: Results of the KiGGS cohort study (second follow-up). *Children*. 2021;8(8):672. doi:[10.3390/children8080672](https://doi.org/10.3390/children8080672)
30. Rubiyah L. International Conference of Early Childhood Education (ICECE 2017). In: Atlantis Press; 2017:1-3. doi:[10.2991/icece-17.2018.1](https://doi.org/10.2991/icece-17.2018.1)
31. Power TG. Parenting dimensions and styles: A brief history and recommendations for future research. *Childhood Obesity*. 2013;9(s1):S-14. doi:[10.1089/chi.2013.0034](https://doi.org/10.1089/chi.2013.0034)
32. APA. Parenting styles. *American Psychological Association (APA)*. Published online 2017. <https://www.apa.org/act/resources/fact-sheets/parenting-styles>
33. Fadlillah M, Wahab R, Ayriza Y, Indartono S. The roles of parenting style towards mental health of early childhood. *Medico-Legal Update*. 2020;20:667-672.
34. Arya H. Authoritarian parenting effects on psychological development of children. Published online September 17, 2021. <https://immunifyme.com/blog/authoritarian-parenting-effects-on-psychological-development-of-children/>
35. Haleema Adnan SR. Effect of Authoritative Parenting Style on Mental Health of Adolescents: Moderating Role of Resilience. Published online April 26, 2022. doi:[10.5281/ZENODO.6486191](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6486191)
36. Heaton KG, Camacho NL, Gaffrey MS. Associations between pre-pandemic authoritative parenting, pandemic stressors, and children's depression and anxiety at the initial stage of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13(1):15592. doi:[10.1038/s41598-023-42268-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42268-x)
37. Uji M, Sakamoto A, Adachi K, Kitamura T. The Impact of Authoritative, Authoritarian, and Permissive Parenting Styles on Children's Later Mental Health in Japan: Focusing on Parent and Child Gender. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. 2014;23(2):293-302. doi:[10.1007/s10826-013-9740-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-013-9740-3)
38. Vyasan N. How authoritative parenting style transforms mental health in children. *News18*. Published online June 2023. <https://www.news18.com/lifestyle/how-authoritative-parenting-style-transforms-mental-health-in-children-8136481.html>
39. Dewar G. The authoritative parenting style: An evidence-based guide. *PARENTING SCIENCE*. Published online April 2023. <https://parentingscience.com/authoritative-parenting-style/>
40. Hayley P. Parenting style and help-seeking for child anxiety and depression: A vignette study. *Digital Commons*. Published online 2022. https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/oa_diss/1459
41. Cherry K. Permissive parenting characteristics and effects. *Verywell Mind*. Published online December 2022. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-permissive-parenting-2794957>
42. Calafat A, García F, Juan M, Becoña E, Fernández-Hermida JR. Which parenting style is more protective against adolescent substance use? Evidence within the european context. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*. 2014;138:185-192. doi:[10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2014.02.705](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2014.02.705)

43. Garcia F, Serra E, Garcia OF, Martinez I, Cruise E. A Third Emerging Stage for the Current Digital Society? Optimal Parenting Styles in Spain, the United States, Germany, and Brazil. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2019;16(13):2333. doi:[10.3390/ijerph16132333](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16132333)
44. Ishak Z, Low S, Lau P. Parenting style as a moderator for students' academic achievement. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*. 2012;21:1-7. doi:[10.1007/s10956-011-9340-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-011-9340-1)
45. Kuppens S, Ceulemans E. Parenting Styles: A Closer Look at a Well-Known Concept. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. 2019;28(1):168-181. doi:[10.1007/s10826-018-1242-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-018-1242-x)
46. Guarnotta E, Troy B. Uninvolved parenting: Definition, characteristics, & impact. *Choosing Therapy*. Published online 2023. <https://www.choosingtherapy.com/uninvolved-parenting/>
47. Mcvoteam. Uninvolved or neglectful parenting: What to know. *Brightside Academy Ohio*. Published online May 2022. <https://brightsideohio.com/uninvolved-neglectful-parenting/>
48. Shiraz Z. Does your parenting style endanger the mental health of your children? *Hindustan Times*. Published online September 2023. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/lifestyle/relationships/does-your-parenting-style-endanger-the-mental-health-of-your-children-101694247457679.html>
49. Pinquart M, Gerke DC. Associations of Parenting Styles with Self-Esteem in Children and Adolescents: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. 2019;28(8):2017-2035. doi:[10.1007/s10826-019-01417-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-019-01417-5)
50. Estee T. Uninvolved parenting - psychological effects on children. *Well Beings Counselling*. Published online May 2022. <https://wellbeingscounselling.ca/uninvolved-parenting-psychological-effects-on-children>
51. Cherry K. Uninvolved parenting and its effects on children. *Verywell Mind*. Published online March 2023. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-uninvolved-parenting-2794958>
52. Shahsavari M. A general overview on parenting styles and its effective factors. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 2012;(6):139-142.
53. Vafaenejad Z, Elyasi F, Moosazadeh M, Shahhosseini Z. *Psychological Factors Contributing to Parenting Styles: A Systematic Review.*; 2019. doi:[10.12688/f1000research.14978.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.14978.2)
54. Zhang Y, Li H. The Relationship between Parenting Styles and Mental Health of College Students: the Mediating Role of Resilience. (1).

Authors

Jean Pierre Mugiraneza received Msc. In Counselling Psychology from Mount Kenya University.

Lambert Kwizera received Msc. in Economics from University of Rwanda.

Ambroise Nzabasanga, is a Master's Candidate in Environmental Economics and Natural Resource management, University of Lay Adventists of Kigali (UNILAK)-Rwanda.

Ildephonse Habinshuti received PhD. in Agro-products Processing and Utilization from the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences.

·University of Rwanda, College of Agriculture, Animal Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, School of Agriculture and Food Sciences, Department of Food Science, P.O. Box 210 Musanze, Rwanda.

·Organization of African Academic Doctors (OAAD), Off Kamiti Road P.O. Box 25305-00100, Nairobi, Kenya.

Felix Banderembaho, PhD Candidate. In Clinical Psychology University of Rwanda/College of Medicine and Health Sciences/School of Medicine and Pharmacy.

Acknowledgements

- **Jean Pierre Mugiraneza:** Writing original draft, Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.
- **Lambert Kwizera:** Writing review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.
- **Ambroise Nzabasanga:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

- **Ildephonse Habinshuti:** Writing review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, supervision.
- **Felix Banderembaho:** Writing review & editing, Supervision.

